

WET REDUCTION OF INSOLUBLE CHROMATES OF SILVER, LEAD AND BARIUM BY SULPHUR DIOXIDE

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In the reduction of insoluble chromates of silver, lead and barium, suspended in water, by $2N\text{-H}_2\text{SO}_3$, chromium sulphate and dithionate are formed invariably in all the three chromates. Both silver and lead are fully converted into their sulphites while barium changes to sulphate. Reaction is very slow and reaches completion only with silver and lead chromates. With barium it stops after some time. Formation of some chromium sulphite is detected only in the reduction of barium chromate.

Reduction of various permanganates has already been studied in this laboratory by Lal *et al.* (this *Journal*, 1955, 32, 65, 547; 1956, 33, 668; 1957, 34, 131). In the present communication the reduction of some insoluble chromates has been studied.

EXPERIMENTAL

Chromates of silver, lead and barium were prepared, purified and analysed to check their purities by standard methods. Fresh samples of $2N$ sulphurous acid were prepared as required.

To 0.5 g. of these chromates, taken in iodine flasks, $2N\text{-H}_2\text{SO}_3$ (50 c.c.) was dropped. The flasks were kept in the dark and shaken occasionally. At different intervals of time the contents were filtered in the dark and in an atmosphere of nitrogen. The investigations were continued by increasing the intervals of time exactly in the same way.

Each filtrate was freed of dissolved SO_2 by passing CO_2 -free air and analysed as recorded below.

The filtrate from silver chromate responded to tests for chromium (green colour), sulphate and dithionate. Traces of sulphite and silver were also detected. Sulphite was stabilised against atmospheric oxidation with glycerol. Silver was removed by adding $0.2N\text{-HCl}$ in a slight excess and the solution left over was made up to a known volume. From an aliquot of this solution chromium was separated as hydroxide and estimated by the oxidation method (Sutton, "A Systematic Handbook of Volumetric Analysis", 1935, 2nd ed., p. 214). The resulting solution was used to estimate sulphate as barium sulphate in cold. Another aliquot was treated with an excess of baryta solution to remove chromium, sulphate and sulphite, if any; dithionate in solution was estimated by oxidation and precipitation as barium sulphate (Mohammad and Ahluwalia, this *Journal*, 1941, 18, 309).

The filtrate obtained in lead chromate reduction responded to tests for chromium, sulphate and dithionate along with traces of lead and sulphite. The sulphite was stabilised with glycerol. Chromium was separated with lead as hydroxide, dissolved in HCl (dil.) and saturated with H_2S to remove any lead present there. The solution was then boiled to expel H_2S , and chromium estimated as before. Sulphate and dithionate were also estimated in the usual way.

TABLE I

Analyses of various reaction mixtures obtained in the reduction of
 Ag_2CrO_4 (0.5 g.) by $2\text{N-H}_2\text{SO}_3$ (50 c.c.).

Total Cr added = 0.07839 g. Total Ag added = 0.3252 g.

Expt. No.	Interval.	Ag_2CrO_4 unchanged	$\text{Cr}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$	$\text{Cr}_2(\text{S}_2\text{O}_8)_3$	Ag_2SO_3	Cr from col. 3, 4 & 5.
1.	19 hrs.	0.40920 g. 0.40760	0.05090 g. 0.05120	0.00730 g. 0.00736	0.08046 g. 0.08140	0.07890 g. 0.07873
2.	3 days and 20 hrs.	0.38170 0.38200	0.06405 0.06620	0.00934 0.00944	0.10450 0.10550	0.07846 0.07908
3.	8 days and 19 hrs.	0.35320 0.35600	0.07984 0.07446	0.01186 0.01137	0.13130 0.12980	0.07861 0.07831
4.	19 days and 21 hrs.	0.13700 0.13650	0.19540 0.19660	0.02920 0.02858	0.32230 0.32280	0.07868 0.07888
5.	75 days	Nil "	0.27140 0.27250	0.04043 0.04060	0.44680 0.44720	0.07920 0.07953

TABLE II

Analyses of various reaction mixtures obtained in the reduction of
 PbCrO_4 (0.5 g.) by $2\text{N-H}_2\text{SO}_3$ (50 c.c.).

Total Cr added = 0.08046 g. Total Pb added = 0.3206 g.

Expt. No.	Intervals.	PbCrO_4 unchanged.	$\text{Cr}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$	$\text{Cr}_2(\text{S}_2\text{O}_8)_3$	PbSO_3	Cr from col. 3, 4 & 5.
1.	21 hrs.	0.18320 g. 0.18180	0.17400 g. 0.17290	0.02606 g. 0.02628	0.28210 g. 0.28280	0.08030 g. 0.07928
2.	37 hrs.	0.15570 0.15480	0.19050 0.18900	0.02783 0.02860	0.30650 0.30690	0.08076 0.07976
3.	61 hrs.	0.10590 0.10770	0.21500 0.21410	0.03164 0.03212	0.35020 0.34880	0.07972 0.07987
4.	22 days and 22 hrs.	0.06821 0.06733	0.23550 0.23657	0.03532 0.03520	0.38240 0.38479	0.08028 0.07990
5.	60 days	Nil "	0.27630 0.27780	0.04116 0.04140	0.44561 0.44600	0.08083 0.08070

The filtrate from barium chromate reactions was found to contain chromium, sulphate, sulphite and dithionate, which were estimated as above.

TABLE III

Analyses of various reaction mixtures obtained in the reduction of
 BaCrO_4 (0.5 g.) by $2\text{N-H}_2\text{SO}_3$ (50 c.c.).

Total Cr added = 0.10263 g. Total Ba added = 0.27106 g.

Expt. No.	Interval	BaCrO_4 unchanged.	$\text{Cr}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$	$\text{Cr}_2(\text{SO}_3)_3$	$\text{Cr}_2(\text{S}_2\text{O}_8)_3$	BaSO_4	Cr from col. 3-6.
1.	3 days and 22 hrs.	0.47000 g. 0.46930	0.00620 g. 0.00600	0.01413 g. 0.01400	0.00304 g. 0.00293	0.02870 g. 0.02850	0.10306 g. 0.10280
2.	9 days and 21 hrs.	0.41720 0.41700	0.01597 0.01542	0.03810 0.03744	0.00892 0.00901	0.07640 0.07710	0.10313 0.10272
3.	14 days and 22 hrs.	0.39510 0.39510	0.01850 0.01920	0.04920 0.04850	0.01210 0.02267	0.09860 0.09900	0.10311 0.10317
4.	34 days and 21 hrs.	0.31460 0.31550	0.03660 0.03820	0.08460 0.08500	0.01770 0.01850	0.17100 0.17120	0.10311 0.10397
5.	The reaction did not reach completion even after a period of 4 months.						

The precipitate in the earlier stages of the reduction of silver chromate consisted of unchanged silver chromate and silver sulphite. Sulphate was absent. Total silver was estimated as chloride. Total chromium was estimated from the silver-free solution and, thus, the values of silver chromate (unchanged) and silver sulphite were calculated. The precipitate in the final experiment was only silver sulphite. Its amount was determined from silver estimated as chloride.

In the earlier stages of lead chromate reduction, the precipitate was found to consist of unchanged lead chromate and lead sulphite only. It was dissolved in excess of HCl (dil.) and both lead and chromium, and subsequently lead chromate and lead sulphite, were determined. The residue in the final experiment was only lead sulphite. It was quickly dissolved in excess of HCl (dil.), glycerol was added and lead and sulphite were estimated by the sulphate and iodometric methods respectively. Sulphate was found absent.

In the reduction of barium chromate, the precipitate was always a mixture of unchanged barium chromate and barium sulphate which were separated by treating with 1:1-HCl and estimated as usual.

DISCUSSION

It is quite evident from the analytical data (Tables I—III) that about 90-91% of total chromium involved is converted into sulphate and the rest (9-10%) to dithionate. The reaction is very slow and the mechanism of various formations may be represented by the chain reactions:

M and M_2 respectively represent the di- and the monovalent metals. The formation of chromium sulphate appears to be a product of the interaction of sulphuric acid, an oxidation product of sulphurous acid, and chromium sesquioxide, a reduction product of chromate ion. Formation of chromium dithionate (about 9-10% of Cr involved) may be due to another side reaction as:

$Cr(SO_3)_2$ is regarded as an intermediate formation in which the valency of chromium remains unchanged. It is further assumed to undergo autooxidation and reduction. SO_3^{2-} ions lose one electron each and dimerise to form $S_2O_6^{2-}$ whereas each Cr^{6+} ion gains 3 electrons and yields Cr^{3+} ion. This shows that sulphite is the precursor of dithionate. The reaction (5) appears to be dominant when the tendency of the reaction to form sulphuric acid is almost negligible; on the other hand, when sulphuric acid is formed in considerable quantity, reaction (4) is favoured. This may be ascribed to the greater chances of the reduction of Cr^{6+} (as in H_2CrO_4) to Cr^{3+} (as in Cr_2O_3) than to its retaining the hexavalency, as in forming $Cr(SO_3)_2$, under the

reducing influence of sulphurous acid. This may lead to the formation of more of sulphuric acid and subsequently of chromium sulphate (reactions 3 and 4 respectively) than dithionate. The effect of acidity on the formation of dithionate is well in line with the observations of Bassett and Henry (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 914) in the oxidation of pyrosulphite by permanganate.

In addition to reaction (3) above, $(M \text{ or } M_2)SO_3$ may partly be oxidised to $(M \text{ or } M_2)SO_4$. But in the case of silver and lead salts in the presence of excess of sulphurous acid, the reaction continues as :

because of the sulphites of these metals having less solubilities in sulphurous acid than their sulphates. At the same time, the net amount of sulphuric acid formed in the reaction remains unchanged. The same does not hold in case of barium sulphate, and therefore barium sulphite does not exist among the products of reaction at any stage. The formation of chromium sulphite is also observed in the latter case due evidently to the sulphuric acid, produced in reaction (3), reacting with barium sulphite in preference to chromium sesquioxide, which is left to react with H_2SO_3 as :

This reaction will continue till the barium is totally converted into sulphate. However, when barium sulphite is completely acted upon, the further production of sulphuric acid yields chromium sulphate, as shown in reaction (4).

The reaction becomes more and more sluggish as the time interval increases. This suggests that probably the particles of the unchanged chromates are covered by a thin film of the adsorbed metal sulphate (silver, lead and barium) which interferes with the normal course of the reaction. In case of silver and lead chromates, these films are again slowly attacked by sulphurous acid and the reaction continues till the chromates are completely acted upon and the metals are converted into their sulphites. Since such a reaction is not possible with barium sulphate, the film of the adsorbed sulphate is not eliminated at all. The film continues to grow in thickness till the reaction stops. The final stage of the reduction of silver and lead chromates may be represented as :

and from the amount of barium chromate reduced, the reaction may be shown as :

Total silver, lead or barium remains always in the precipitate, each of the first two as sulphite and the third as sulphate. In the reduction of silver and lead chromates, the total sulphate and Cr (III) formed remain in the filtrate, chromium being accounted for as sulphate and dithionate, whereas in the reduction of barium chromate, total sulphate is distributed among the precipitate as well as the filtrate and chromium is accounted for as sulphate, sulphite and dithionate.